

ISSN No: 3433-7029

abstrajournals.com

892 Berne St SE, Atlanta, GA 30316, United States

Abstra International Journal of Economics and Finance

Volume 14 Issue 1, January 2025

59

ENTREPRENEURIAL RISK-TAKING ON MARKETING PERFORMANCE OF SMES IN OSAKWE INDUSTRIAL CLUSTER, AWADA, ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

Dr. Okeke, Adaora Florence¹

¹ Department of Marketing, Chukwuemeka Odimegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State

How to Cite this Paper:

Okeke, Adaora Florence (2025). Entrepreneurial Risk-Taking on Marketing Performance of SMES in Osakwe Industrial Cluster, Awada, Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Management* 14(1), 059-074

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14980807>

Corresponding Author

Dr. Okeke, Adaora Florence

Keywords

Risk-taking, customer patronage, customer retention, Osakwe Industrial Cluster

Abstract

This study examined the effect of entrepreneurial risk-taking on marketing performance of SMES in Osakwe Industrial Cluster, Awada, Anambra State, Nigeria. The study adopted a cross-sectional unidirectional descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 75 SMES in Osakwe Industrial Cluster, Awada, Anambra State, Nigeria. Taro Yamane formula was used to determine sample size of 227, while convenience sampling was used to select the sample units. The data obtained from the field survey was presented with simple descriptive statistics such as tables, charts and percentages. All stated hypotheses in the study were tested with simple regression model using the SPSS software version 25.0. The study revealed that risk-taking is a positive and significant factor influencing customer patronage of SMES in Osakwe Industrial Cluster, Awada, Anambra State, Nigeria. Also, risk-taking was found to be statistically significant and positively related to customer retention of SMES in Osakwe Industrial Cluster, Awada, Anambra State, Nigeria. It was concluded that entrepreneurial risk-taking exerts statistically significant and positive effect on marketing performance SMES in Osakwe Industrial Cluster, Awada, Anambra State, Nigeria. The study recommended that the managers of the SMES in Osakwe Industrial Cluster, Awada, Anambra State, Nigeria should encourage risk-taking in new initiatives and project planning processes.

INTRODUCTION

No business is managed without risk. Risk taking is the foremost component of entrepreneurial orientation. As the business grows, firm faces numerous kinds of risks in terms of finance, competition, latest technology; political party and their new policies etc. These all risks give an impact on the performance of the business (Baker & Sinkula, 2009). Risk taking is the act of taking a decision or performing a task that may lead to positive or negative outcome in order to achieve a goal. It is the propensity of an SME to make gutsy moves such as entering unfamiliar new markets, obligating a huge percentage of the firm's resources to investments with unknown outcomes and taking up of big loans (Coulthard, 2007; Baker & Sinkula, 2009).

Anambra State of Nigeria is endowed with several industrial clusters across the state. Osakwe Industrial cluster, Awada in Anambra State is one of such industrial clusters. The industries cover a wide range of products: plastic film extrusion, plastic pipe extrusion, plastic injection, plastic blow molding, polythene bag making, and plastic waste recycling (Ifediora, 2006). However, the realization of the full potential of this industrial cluster has been dampened by the adoption of inappropriate industrialization policies at different times. Several policy interventions that were aimed at stimulating entrepreneurship development through small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) promotion by governors of the zone have failed to achieve the desired goals, as it has produced indigenous entrepreneurs who are basically distribution agents of imported products, as opposed to the desired objective of building in-country entrepreneurial capacity for manufacturing, mechanized agriculture, improved outputs and experts needed for rapid industrialization.

Studies have indicated that in the current economic condition in Nigeria, academic scholars and enthusiastic entrepreneurs are interested to examine the critical issues of measuring business performance via the strategic influence of entrepreneurial risk-taking (Wales, Covin & Monsen, 2020). Pizarro-Moreno, Real & Sousa-Ginel, (2007), argued that companies need to regenerate themselves as a result of frequent environmental changes experienced by businesses through entrepreneurial risk-taking.

Performance is the main indicator to measure the success of any organization. It can be defined as an operational ability with respect to satisfy the needs of various parties like customers, creditors, owners and society (Ford & Schellenberg, 1982, Dess & Robinson, 1984). Strong marketing performance among SMEs can play a crucial role in boosting their competitiveness, resilience, effectiveness, sustainability and efficiency. Omhonria and Needorn (2022) posited that performance depict the degree at which a corporate entity achieves its missions as it relates to work outcomes, customers relationship, quality service and overall wellbeing. Aligning with the above definition of firm's performance, it implies that the performance of an SME will encompass both financial and non-financial aspect of the enterprise.

In measuring performance, several indicators have been used which includes constructs like profitability, competitiveness, employee satisfaction, operational efficiency, capacity utilization, goal achievement, increase patronage, customers satisfaction, efficiency, effectiveness and survival (Omhonria & Needorn, 2022, Chen, Jiang, Jia & Liu, 2021).

The literature on entrepreneurial orientation (EO) and entrepreneurial risk-taking (as a dimension of EO) discuss the relationship between an enterprise's risk-taking and business performance (Arabeche, Soudani, Brahmi, Aldieri, Vinci & Abdelli, 2022). However, few studies on EO-performance have been conducted among SMEs (Rochdi, Khatijah & Muhammad, 2017; Arabeche, Soudani & Abdelli, 2021; Arabeche, et al., 2022). Thus, the enterprise risk-taking-performance relationship suggests the need for further research from the Anambra industrial cluster perspective. Hence, the scope of this paper offers a deeper assessment of the effect of entrepreneurial risk-taking on the marketing performance of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of entrepreneurial risk-taking on marketing performance of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria. Specifically, the aims were to;

- i. ascertain the effect of entrepreneurial risk-taking on customer patronage
- ii. investigate the effect of entrepreneurial risk-taking on customer retention

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Risk-Taking

The concept of risk-taking has been long associated with entrepreneurship. Early definition of entrepreneurship centered on the willingness of entrepreneurs to engage in calculated business risks, [Lumpkin and Dess \(1996\)](#). [Oscar, Zheng and Hung \(2013\)](#) identified venturing into the unknown as a generally accepted definition for risk taking, though may be difficult to quantify. This is because, in addition to monetary risk, it typically entails psychological and social risks ([Lumpkin & Dess, 1996](#)). Risk taking is also perceived as tendency towards risky projects ([Miller 1983, Covin & Stevin, 1988; Mario, 2013](#)). It was expected that firms that have better performance would also have a higher level of risk propensity ([Leko-Simic & Horvat, 2013](#)). [Leko-Simic and Horvat, \(2013\)](#) further emphasized that risk-taking propensity can be defined as a tendency to take or avoid risks, which is viewed as an individual characteristic.

The positive relationship between risk-taking propensity and risk decision making by individuals is expected to translate to organizations through top management teams. Although there are many ways of conceptualizing risk, [Oscar et al., \(2013\)](#) described entrepreneurs' perception of risk as the uncertainty and potential losses associated with outcomes which may follow from a given set of actions or behaviour. Risk taking depends on risk propensity and risk perception. That is, the higher the risk propensity, the lower the anxiety over risk or risk taking. Risk can also be associated with willingness to commit large amount of resources to a project which the probable cost and chances of failure are high ([Keh, Nguyen & Ng, 2007; Baker & Sinkula, 2009](#)).

SMEs' Performance

Different firm performance estimations have been connected in earlier business research. In any case, the lion's share of these examinations did not give any support to the choice of measures utilized ([Murphy, Trailer & Hill 1996](#)). Measuring business performance is pivotal for business management, and it is usually associated with the average rate of return maintained over a period of years ([Barney, 2002; Mackey, Jackey & Barney 2007](#)). In this study, two non-financial indices were used to measure performance of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial Cluster, Awada, Anambra State of Nigeria. They are briefly captured below;

Customer Patronage

In the context of marketing, patronage is an exchange process where one receives a service or goods in exchange for money or other considerations. Customer patronage is therefore, the purchase of goods and service from a vendor by a customer or a business. Firms that crave sustained patronage in today's highly competitive business environment are required to have the satisfaction of their customers as a primary focus. Customer patronage represents the degree to which buying units concentrate purchases over time to a given product or brand based on positive reinforcement and expressed through repetitive buying behaviour ([Nyakweba, Wesonga, & Bosire, 2015](#)).

Customer patronage also deals with the processes that customers engage in when selecting a product or brand among alternatives; as well as the factors and attributes used in the selection. Behavioural scientists thus propose that customer patronage results from a trial that gets reinforced through satisfaction, and leads to repeat purchase; while cognitive psychologists contend that customer patronage builds through mental processes, based on the believe that consumers engage in extensive problem-solving behaviour involving services ([Nyakweba et al., 2015](#)). Customer patronage important is essential to business sustainability in the confectionery business industry. Hence, marketers strive to determine customers' preference with a view to adapt or generate value that elicits customer patronage ([Njite, Njoroge, Parsa, Parsa & van der Rest, 2015](#)).

Customer Retention

Customer retention can be defined as how small businesses or organizations are able to sustain their existing customers based on creating cordial relations with those who

patronize the company's product, (Kotler, 2008). Customer retention is a strategically driven approach based on customer behaviour. Customer retention signifies customer's inclinations, identification, commitment, trust and willingness to stick with a brand, (Rather, Tehseen, Itoo & Hussain, 2019). It also implies a continuing commitment on the part of customers to maintain a long-lasting relationship with a brand (Cook, 2002).

Customer retention is very fundamental because the cost of acquiring new customers can be five times tedious than that of retaining existing and current ones; also, retained customers pay less attention to the frolics of competing brands, they are less price-sensitive and spread favourable word-of-mouth, (Ama, 2019). It is easier and less expensive to retain customers than to acquire them. The probability of selling to an existing customer is at least 40% more likely than converting someone who has never bought from you before. The probability of selling to an existing customer is 60% - 70% while the probability of selling to a new prospect is 5%-20% (Patel, 2018). Customer retention is a metric that measures customer loyalty or the ability for an organization to keep its customers over time. It can help to identify the number of loyal customers

Risk-Taking and SMEs' Performance

Risk-taking in an organisation can emerge from financial and non-financial risk (Khemakhem & Boujelbene, 2018). Over time, the significance of these entrepreneurial risks (financial and non-financial) had been widely investigated in the research model (Mohsni, Isaac & Saquib, 2021; Shahzad, Lu & Fareed, 2019). Insights from the available literature revealed a significant relationship between risk taking and SMEs' performance (Mohsni et al., 2021; Shahzad et al., 2019). Results obtained from the studies by Chen and Ma (2011) and Shahzad et al., (2019) revealed that risk-taking abilities might have both positive and negative impact on SMEs' performance.

The study of Zimmerer & Scarborough, (2005) argued that taking risks during uncertain periods, risk-taking abilities propels a firm to perform better than those averting risk. Furthermore, studies not limited to Kosa, Mohammad and Ajibia (2018), Kraus et al. (2011), and Lumpkin and Dess (2001) argued a significant relationship between risk-taking behaviour and SMEs' performance. Contrarily, Roux and Bengesi (2014) study posited a significant negative relationship between entrepreneurial risk-taking and SMEs' performance. The findings from Roux and Bengesi (2014) conformed to that of Chen and Ma (2011) and Shahzad et al. (2019). Although findings from the studies of Chen and Ma (2011) and Shahzad et al. (2019) supported both positive and negative findings, these scholars' negative relationship concerns individual risk-taking behaviours that impede organisational risks behaviour.

Theoretical Framework

Resource-based View Theory

This study is based on the foundation of the resource-based view (RBV) theory propounded by Barney (1991). The RBV is used because it explains the relationship between the independent and the dependent variables of the study. The literature on entrepreneurship has primarily applied the RBV theory, which looks at how a firm's resources can be used to sustain the firm in light of competitive advantages. RBV identifies firms' resources like tangible, such as physical assets, and intangible resources, such as knowledge, skills, and competencies; the latter are also the attributes that drive profitability, growth, and ultimately, the firm's survival (Agyapong & Attram, 2019). This view holds these resources as scarce, valuable, and imitable by competitors (Barney, Ketchen & Wright 201).

Firms' managers are expected to analyze resources, select strategies and resources, and then appraise capabilities to achieve competitive advantages against other firms. EO in RBV entails the activities, processes, behaviours, and decision-making styles that have become critical elements in achieving the sustainable competitive advantages of SMEs (Kraus et al., 2011); this has implications for the selection, usage, management, and disposition of firms' financial assets (Nunooandoh & Darfor 2015). Eniola and Ektebong (2016) stated that SMEs sustain their competitive advantage through unique, tacit, tangible,

and intangible resources contributing to their performances. New firms must have productive resources to create a competitive advantage that can enhance survival or growth (Yin et al., 2020).

Schumpeter's Innovation Theory

Schumpeter (1942) pioneered in highlighting the role of innovation in entrepreneurial process. Schumpeter (1942) described a process of "creative destruction" where wealth creation occurs through disruption of existing market structures due to the introduction of new goods and/or services that cause resources to move away from existing firms to new ones thus allowing the growth of the new firms. Accordingly, Schumpeter called innovation the specific tool of entrepreneurs, the means by which entrepreneurs exploit change as an opportunity for a different business or a different service.

Schumpeter (1942) stressed the role of entrepreneurs as primary agents effecting creative destruction, and emphasized to the entrepreneurs the need to search purposefully for the sources of innovation, the changes and their symptoms that indicate opportunities for successful innovation; as well as their need to know and to apply the principles of successful innovation. This Schumpeterian manner of thinking has been carried forward by successive scholars and researchers (Drucker 1985; Lumpkin & Dess, 1996; Shane, Covered & Westhead, 1991).

Schumpeterian growth theory supposes that technological progress comes from innovations carried out by firms motivated by the pursuit of profit. That is, each innovation is aimed at creating some new process or product that gives its creator a competitive advantage over its business rivals; it does so by rendering obsolete some previous innovation; and it is in turn destined to be rendered obsolete by future innovations (Schumpeter, 1934).

Empirical Studies

Abshar and Seprizola (2023) studied the Influence of entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation on SMEs business performance in Padang. The population of the study consisted solely of Padang-based SMEs. 100 samples of SMEs in Padang City were collected. Using a standardized questionnaire, respondents were asked to rate their entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation in an effort to enhance the success of their firm. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21 and multiple regression analysis. The findings revealed that entrepreneurial orientation has a significant positive influence on business performance variables.

Adibe, Akam and Onuorah (2023) examined the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on performance of selected small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Southeast Nigeria. The study was anchored on Resources Based View theory and Entrepreneurial Orientation Theory. A descriptive survey design was carried out using the sampled managers and business owners in the selected SMEs. The study population was 2093 while the sample size was 404 arrived at using Borg and Gall (1973) formula. Data were collected using self-administered questionnaire. Descriptive statistics (distribution tables, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (Pearson correlation co-efficient and regression analysis) were used in the study. The study revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between entrepreneurial orientation dimensions (entrepreneurial risk-taking, entrepreneurial proactiveness, entrepreneurial competitive aggressiveness, entrepreneurial innovation, entrepreneurial autonomy on SMEs performance in Southeast, Nigeria.

Nwachukwu and Onuoha (2022) examined the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and corporate performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Lagos State, Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey was used and a population of 2596 SMEs in Lagos State was covered. A sample size of 310 was drawn from the population and the simple random sampling was adopted. Data were gathered using copies of questionnaire. The Spearman Rank Order Correlation was used in testing the hypotheses so as to ascertain the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and corporate performance. The result indicated a significant relationship between the dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation

(innovativeness and risk-taking) with the measures of corporate performance (profitability and operational efficiency).

[Oghenevwegba and Iwegbue \(2022\)](#) evaluated the impact of entrepreneurial orientation in the performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Asaba, Delta State. Entrepreneurial Orientation was measured with Proactiveness (PRO), Innovations (INVT), Risk Taking Propensity (RTP) and Competitive Aggressiveness (CA) in relation to the PSME in Nigeria. A total of 100 copies of the questionnaire were administered but 87 were returned and properly filled. Descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and multiple regression analysis were used in the study with the aid of SPSS version 23. Findings obtained from the analysis, revealed that PRO, INVT, RTP and CA have significant relationship with PSME in Nigeria.

[Ologbenla \(2022\)](#) carried out a study on the topic “Entrepreneurial orientation and performance control attributes among SMEs in Osun State Nigeria”. A sample of 340 SMEs was selected across the states using both multistage and random sampling techniques. The variables of entrepreneurial orientation include innovativeness, proactiveness, and risk-taking. While the performance control attribute is the dependent variable. Descriptive and inferential statistics results showed that ordinal regression and spearman rank correlation results were more suitable for the analysis. The result showed that all the three variables of entrepreneurial orientation namely innovativeness, proactiveness, and risk-taking were very important for an SME owner to develop a good performance control attribute.

[Ilesanmi, Onikoyi and Badiru \(2022\)](#) studied the impact of Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) on the organisational performance of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Lagos State, Nigeria. A simple random sampling technique was adopted, and 448 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved and analyzed from 520 administered among SMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria. The results of the analysis revealed that the combination of five major drivers of EO (Innovativeness, Proactiveness, Risk-Taking, Autonomy and Competitive Aggressiveness) have significant impact on SMEs innovation in Lagos State.

[Kuta, Abdulwaheed and Enesi \(2022\)](#) investigated the effects of entrepreneurial orientation and customer orientation on bakeries’ performance. Stratified sampling technique was employed to study a total of 105 out of 130 SMEs that specialized in baking of bread and other flour products. The owner-manager 5-point likert scale questionnaire was designed and served both online and offline to address the survey questions. Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) technique was employed to assess the measurement and structural models indicators. The results of the study showed that entrepreneurial orientation dimensions (innovativeness, proactiveness, risk taking, autonomy and competitive aggressiveness) have significant effect on bakery performance.

[Alam et al. \(2022\)](#) examined the relationships between entrepreneurial orientation (EO) and business performances of Malay-based SMEs in Malaysia. The research model for the study was drawn from the literature on entrepreneurship. This study identified five entrepreneurial orientations and tested hypotheses on which EO has a significant influence on business performance with empirical data from a sample of 407 Malay-based SMEs in Malaysia. The PLS regression analysis showed that risk-taking, proactiveness, innovativeness, and achievement factors were the significant elements of entrepreneurship orientation.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted a cross-sectional descriptive survey research design. A survey approach was ideal for an investigative study of this nature. It is drawn out to determine the subtle elements of the strategies vital for getting data to structure or take care of the examination issue ([Malhotra et al., 2012](#)). The decision of research design can rely upon whether the examination means to test, find or develop hypotheses ([Gill & Johnson, 2010](#)). [Creswell \(2009\)](#) has referred to three plans specifically; qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods.

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised 74 SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Awada, Anambra State of Nigeria.

Sample size of the Study

The 77 SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria have about 1800 employees (www.afriheritage.org). Using the Yamane's equation, the sample size was;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where n = sample size

N = Total population

e = error (0.05)

Note: Here, the researcher assumes a 5% level of significance (95% confidence level).

$$\text{Thus } n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{1800}{1 + 1800(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1800}{1 + 1800(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{1800}{6.5}$$

n = 277 respondents.

Therefore, a sample size of 277 respondents was used for the study.

Sampling Procedure

Convenience sampling which is a non-probability sampling method was employed in the study because it offered the researcher the opportunity to select and interview those who were willing to provide the relevant information needed for the study. The researcher approached these respondents in their enterprises where copies of the questionnaire were administered to them and retrieved after completion. Based on a total sample size of 277, copies of the questionnaire were administered.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data obtained from the field survey were presented with simple descriptive statistics. All stated hypotheses in the study were tested with simple regression model using the SPSS software version 25.0.

Presentation of Data

A total of 277 (two hundred and seventy-seven) copies of questionnaire were administered to the respondents from Osakwe Industrial Cluster, Awada, Anambra State of Nigeria. Out of this number, two hundred and seventy (270) copies were retrieved and the remaining seven (7) copies were not returned.

Entrepreneurial Risk-Taking

Table 1: Risk-taking of the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria

Statement items	Item Statistics			
	Mean	S.D	N	Remark
I am comfortable taking risks to grow my business	4.24	.661	270	Supported
I feel anxious when faced with uncertain business outcomes	3.34	1.233	270	Supported
I carefully analyze risks before making business decisions	4.56	.681	270	Supported
I believe taking risk is essential for entrepreneurial success	4.82	.562	270	Supported

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 1 shows the mean scores and standard deviations of the responses of the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria on innovativeness. The criterion for mean score acceptance was 3.0. The table above showed that “I am comfortable taking risks to grow my business” had a mean score of 4.24, “I feel anxious when faced with uncertain business outcomes” had a mean score of 3.34. Also, “I carefully analyze risks before making business decisions” had a mean score of 4.56, while “I believe taking risk is essential for entrepreneurial success” had a mean score of 4.82. Based on the criteria for mean acceptance, the above statement items were positively correlated to risk-taking and further shows that risk-taking exists in the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria.

Customer Patronage

Table 2: Customer patronage of the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria

Statement item	Item Statistics			
	Mean	S.D	N	Remark
Customers frequently buy products and services from this business	3.83	.680	270	Supported
Customers feel satisfied with the quality of products and services offered by this business	4.62	.554	270	Supported
Customers recommend the business to their friends and associates	4.48	.591	270	Supported

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 2 shows the mean scores and standard deviations of the responses of the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria on customer patronage. The criterion for mean score acceptance was 3.0. The table above showed that “Customers frequently buy products and services from this business” had a mean score of 3.88, “Customers feel satisfied with the quality of products and services offered by this business” had a mean score of 4.62. Also, “Customers recommend the business to their friends and associates” had a mean score of 4.48. Based on the criteria for mean acceptance, the above statement items were positively correlated to customer patronage and further shows that customer patronage is positive in the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria.

Customer Retention

Table 3: Customer retention of the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria

Statement items	Item Statistics			Remark
	Mean	S.D	N	
Customers consistently choose this business over competitors	4.55	.551	270	Supported
Customers regularly buy products from this business	4.37	.591	270	Supported
The business consistently meets and exceed customers expectation	4.11	.615	270	Supported
Customers feel excited whenever they buy from this business	3.98	1.488	270	Supported

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 3 shows the mean scores and standard deviations of the responses of the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria on customer retention. The criterion for mean score acceptance was 3.0. The table above showed that “Customers consistently choose this business over competitors” had a mean score of 4.55, “Customers regularly buy products from this business” had a mean score of 4.37. Also, “The business consistently meets and exceed customers’ expectation” had a mean score of 3.11, while “Customers feel excited whenever they buy from this business” had a mean score of 3.98. Based on the criteria for mean acceptance, the above statement items were positively correlated to customer retention and further shows that customer retention is positively pursued in the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria.

Test of Hypotheses

Effect risk-taking on customer patronage of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria

Table 4: Simple regression analysis showing the effect of risk-taking on customer patronage of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria

Model	Coefficients ^a				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.299	.237		5.470	.000
Risk-taking	1.195	.053	.759	22.334	.000
R	.591				
R ²	.583				
F-Statistics	67.450				

Dependent Variable: Customer Patronage Source: Field Survey, 2024

In Table 4.6, risk-taking was found to be a positive and significant factor influencing customer patronage of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria. Risk-taking was significant at 1% probability level and positively affects customer patronage of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria. This indicates that customer patronage of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria increases with an increase in risk-taking. Thus, as a way of increasing customer patronage, the risk-taking by the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria is important. This assertion is at the 99% confidence level. The R Square of 0.583 shows that 58% of the variability observed in customer patronage was explained by risk-taking. The other 42% were due to some other factors that were not included in the model. The f-statistics of 67.450 which was significant at the 1% level shows that the model has a good fit. It can thus be concluded that risk-taking has significant and positive effect on customer patronage of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria

Effect of risk-taking on customer retention of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria

Table 5: Simple regression analysis showing the effect of risk-taking on customer retention of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria

Model	Coefficients ^a				
	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.331	.136		17.176	.000
Risk-taking	.520	.031	.663	17.000	.000
R	.733				
R ²	.699				
F-Statistics	56.648				

Dependent Variable: Customer Retention

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Simple regression result in Table 4.8 shows the effect of risk-taking on customer retention of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria. From the simple regression analysis table, risk-taking was found to be statistically significant at the 1% probability level with P-Value = 0.000 and with a positive figure. This implies that an increase in risk-taking in the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria will result to a corresponding increase in customer retention. The coefficient of determination (r^2) value of 0.699 shows that 70% of the variation in customer retention of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria was accounted for by risk-taking. The other 30% were due to some other factors that were not included in the model. Similarly, the f-statistics value of 56.648 indicates that the model specification was correct while significant at 1%. The estimated regression line shows that customer retention of the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria is a linear function of risk-taking. This assertion is at the 99% confidence level. Therefore, it can be concluded that risk-taking has significant effect on customer retention of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The essence of the study was to evaluate and examine entrepreneurial risk-taking and its effect on the marketing performance of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria. The study showed that risk-taking was a positive and significant factor affecting customer patronage and retention of the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria. This is in agreement with previous findings. [Olubiyi et al. \(2019\)](#) have revealed that risk taking had positive significant effect on customer retention. Also, [Abdalla and Mohamed \(2020\)](#) investigated the effect of entrepreneurial orientation (EO) on firms' performance and their findings revealed that risk-taking has a significant effect on customer retention.

Equally, [Ali et al. \(2020\)](#) in their findings on the effect of entrepreneurial orientation, market orientation and total quality management on performance showed that risk-taking is positively and significantly related to customer satisfaction of SMEs. [Aroyeun et al. \(2019\)](#) also revealed that risk taking initiative has positive significant effect on patronage. [Bonaventure et al. \(2017\)](#) revealed a positive and significant relationship between risk-taking and measures of organizational performance which includes customer patronage.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study assessed the effect of entrepreneurial risk-taking on the marketing performance of SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria. The results obtained in this empirical research allow us to conclude that the higher the entrepreneurial risk-taking of the studied SMEs in Osakwe Industrial cluster, Anambra State of Nigeria, the higher the level of performance they will have in terms customer patronage and customer retention.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

- i. SMEs in Osakwe Industrial Cluster, Awada, Anambra State of Nigeria should not fear failure, as calculated risk-taking contributes to an organization's growth. Aversion towards risk taking can lead to a slow and gradual downside in a firm's performance, culminating in a total debacle.
- ii. SMEs in Osakwe Industrial Cluster, Awada, Anambra State of Nigeria should increase the risk-taking spirit of their employees, as it is one of the most important factors affecting entrepreneurial mind-set on the one hand, and its effectiveness in raising the performance of SMEs.

References

- Adibe, G. C., Akam, G. U. & Onuorah, A. N. (2023). Entrepreneurial Orientation and Performance of Selected Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Southeast, Nigeria. *International Academic Journal of Management and Marketing*, 7(3), 107-129
- Adisa, M. K., Adeoye, A. O., & Okunbanjo, O. I. (2016). The impact of entrepreneurship orientation on entrepreneurs' compensation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Management Studies*, 3(3), 102-116.
- Agyapong, A., Maledidong, P. D., & Mensah, H. K. (2020). Performance outcome of entrepreneurial behavior of SMEs in a developing economy: the role of international mind-set. *Journal of Strategy and Management*, 1-19.
- Ahimbisibwe, G. M., & Abaho, E. (2013). Export entrepreneurial orientation and export performance of SMEs in Uganda. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Management and Business Studies*, 2(1), 56- 62.
- Al-Homoud, W. (2018). The effect of intellectual capital and entrepreneurial orientation on the level of service innovation in the retail chain pharmacy industry in Jordan: A case study on pharmacy one (Master Dissertation, Faculty of Economic and Administrative Sciences, Yarmouk University).
- AlKuaik, K.O., (2017). Impact of network relational and structural embeddedness on firm's innovation: a study at the Saudi firm's level (Doctoral dissertation, University of Strathclyde)
- Almomani, R. Z. Q., Al-Abbadi, L. H. M., Rumman, A. R. A. A. A., Abu-Rumman, A., & Banyhamdan, K. (2019). Organizational memory, knowledge management, marketing innovation and cost of quality: Empirical effects from construction industry in Jordan, *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal*, 25(3), 1–13.
- Alzuod, M. (2014). *The influence of managerial innovation on firm performance in Jordanian commercial banks* (Master Dissertation, Hashemite University).
- Anlesinya, A., Eshun, P., & Bonuedi, A. F. (2015). Entrepreneurial orientation dimensions and profitability nexus: evidence from micro enterprises in the retail sector in a developing country. *International Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Research*, 3(7), 79-87.
- Arabeche, Z., Soudani, A., & Abdelli, M. E. A. (2021). Entrepreneurial Orientation and Firm Performance in Algerian Small and Medium Enterprises. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 10(11), 55-65.
- Arabeche, Z., Soudani, A., & Abdelli, M. E. A. (2021). Entrepreneurial Orientation and Firm Performance in Algerian Small and Medium Enterprises. *International Journal of*

- Business and Management Invention*, 10(11), 55-65.
- Arabeche, Z., Soudani, A., Brahmi, M., Aldieri, L., Vinci, C. P. & Abdelli, M. E. A. (2022). Entrepreneurial Orientation, Organizational Culture and Business Performance in SMEs: Evidence from Emerging Economy. *Sustainability*, 14, 5160. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14095160>
- Arisi-Nwugballa, E. A., Elom M. A., & Onyeizugbe, C. U. (2016). Evaluating the relevance of entrepreneurial orientation to the performance of micro, small and medium enterprises in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 6(3), 1-12
- Arshi, T. A. (2016). *Entrepreneurial orientation and its impact on innovation intensity in the Omani corporate sector* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Bedfordshire).
- Baba, R., & Elumalai, S. (2011). Entrepreneurial orientation of SMEs in Labuan and its effects on performance. *Working Paper Series No. 1113*. Malaysia.
- Baker, W. E. & Sinkula, J. M. (2009). The complementary effects of market orientation and entrepreneurial orientation on profitability in small businesses. *J. Small Bus. Manage.*, 47, 443-464
- Baker, W. E., & Sinkula, J. M. (2009). The complementary effects of market orientation and entrepreneurial orientation on profitability in small businesses. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 47(4), 443-464.
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99-120. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/014920639101700108>
- Barney, J. B. (2002). *Gaining and sustaining competitive advantage*. Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ.
- Barringer, B. R. and Harrison, J. S., (2000). Walking a tightrope: Creating value through interorganizational relationships. *Journal of management*, 26(3), pp.367-403.
- Brownhilder, N. N. & Johan, V. Z. (2017). Entrepreneurial orientation and its impact on firm growth amongst SMEs in South Africa. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 15(3), 166-178.
- Castanias, R., & Helfat, C. (1991). Managerial resources and rents. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 155–171.
- Chen, L., Jiang, M., Jia, F., & Liu, G. (2021). Artificial intelligence adoption in business-to-business marketing: Toward a conceptual framework. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*,
- Covin, J. G., & Slevin, D. P. (1988). Strategic management of small firms in hostile and benign environments. *Strategic Management Journal*, 10, 75-87. doi:10.1002/smj.4250100107
- Covin, J. G., & Wales, W. J. (2012). The Measurement of Entrepreneurial Orientation. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 36, 677–702.
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage Publications: Los Angeles, USA.

- Deakins, D., & Freel, M. (2012). *Entrepreneurship and small firms*. 6th ed. McGraw Hills Higher Education.
- Dess, G. G., & Lumpkin, G. T. (2005). The role of entrepreneurial orientation in stimulating effective corporate entrepreneurship. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 19(1), 147-156.
- Dess, G. G., & Robinson Jr, R. B. (1984). Measuring organizational performance in the absence of objective measures: the case of the privately-held firm and conglomerate business unit. *Strategic Management Journal*, 5(3), 265-273.
- Dess, G. G., Robinson, R. B., Jr. (1984). Measuring organizational performance in the absence of objective measures: The case of the privately-held firm and conglomerate business unit. *Strategic Management Journal*, 5, 265–273.
- Drucker, P. (1985). *Innovation and entrepreneurship*, New York: Harper & Row
- Eniola, A.A., (2020). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy and orientation for SME development. *Small Enterprise Research*, 27(2), pp.125-145.
- Fairoz, F. M., Hirobumi, T., & Tanaka, Y. (2010). Entrepreneurial orientation and business performance of small and medium scale enterprises of Hambantota District Sri Lanka. *Asian Social Science*, 6(3), 34.
- Falahat, M., Soto-Acosta, P., & Ramayah, T. (2022). Analysing the importance of international knowledge, orientation, networking and commitment as entrepreneurial culture and market orientation in gaining competitive advantage and international performance. *Int. Mark. Rev.* 39, 463–481. doi: 10.1108/IMR-02-2021-0053
- Ibrahim, A. U., & Martins, M. A. (2020). Influence of entrepreneurial orientation on firms' performance: Evidence from small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 10(2), 99-118.
- Irawan, T. T., Bin-Mansor, N. M. & Ramlee, A. A. (2023). Entrepreneurial Orientation and Firm Performance: A Systematic Review. *European Business & Management*, 9(3), 51-62
- Isichei, E. E., Agbaeze, K. E., & Odiba, M. O. (2020). Entrepreneurial orientation and performance in SMEs. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 15(6), 1219- 1241. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOEM-08-2019-0671>.
- Kamasak, R. (2017). The contribution of tangible and intangible resources, and capabilities to a firm's profitability and market performance. *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*.
- Keh, H. T., Nguyen, T. T., & Ng, H. P. (2007).The effects of entrepreneurial orientation and market information on the performance of SMEs. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 22(4), 592-611
- Khemakhem, S., & Boujelbene, Y. (2018). Credit risk prediction: A comparative study between discriminant analysis and the neural network approach. *Accounting and Management Information Systems*, 14(1), 60
- Kothari, C. R. (2003). *Research Methodology*. New Delhi, New Age International (p) Ltd.

- Kotler, P. (2008). *Marketing management*. New York: Prentice Hall.
- Kraus, S., Rigtering, J. P. C., Hughes, M. & Hosman, V. (2012). Entrepreneurial orientation and the business performance of SMEs: a quantitative study from The Netherlands. *Review of Managerial Science*, 6, 161-182, doi: 10.1007/s11846-011-0062-
- Krauss, S. I., Frese, M., Friedrich, C., & Unger, J. M. (2011). Entrepreneurial orientation: A psychological model of success among southern African small business owners. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 14(3), 315-344.
- Kropp, F., Lindsay, N. J., & Shoham, A. (2018). Entrepreneurial orientation and international entrepreneurial business venture startup. *Int. J. Entrep. Behav. Res.*, 14, 102–117. doi: 10.1108/13552550810863080
- Kuta, D. C., Abdulwaheed, D., & Enesi, B. I. (2022). Effect of entrepreneurial orientation and customer orientation on bakery performance. *Journal of Business Management, Innovation and Creativity*, 1(1), 1-14
- Lechner, C. & Gudmundsson, S. V. (2014). Entrepreneurial orientation, firm strategy and small firm performance. *International Small Business Journal*, 32(1), 36-60.
- Leko-simic, M., & Horvat, Jasna. (2013). Risk taking Propensity and Export Performance of Croatian Exporters. *International Research Journal*, 4, (4), 324
- Lomberg, C., Urbig, D., Stöckmann, C., Marino, L. D., & Dickson, P. H. (2017). Entrepreneurial orientation: The dimensions' shared effects in explaining firm performance. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 41(6), 973-998.
- Lumpkin, G. T. & Dess, G. G. (1996). Clarifying the entrepreneurial orientation construct and linking it to performance. *Academy of Management Review*, 21(1), 135–173.
- Mackey, A., Jackey, T. B., & Barney, J. B. (2007). Corporate social responsibility and firm performance: Investor preferences and corporate strategies. *Academy of Management Review*, 32(3), 817–835.
- Malhotra, N. K., Birks, D. F. & Wills, P., (2012). *Marketing Research: An Applied Approach*. 4th Ed., Essex: Pearson Education.
- Man, T. W. Y., & Lau, T. (2005). The context of entrepreneurship in Hong Kong: an investigation through the patterns of entrepreneurial competencies in contrasting industrial environments. *J. Small Bus. Enterp. Dev.* 12, 464–481. doi: 10.1108/14626000510628162
- Mohsni, S., Isaac, O., & Saquib, S. (2021). Board gender diversity, firm performance and risk-taking in developing countries: The moderating effect of culture. *Journal of International Financial Markets Institutions and Money*, 73, 101360.
- Murphy, G. B., Trailer, G. & Hill, R. C. (1996). Measuring performance in entrepreneurship research. *Journal of Business Research*, 36(1), 15-23.
- Nigerian Ministry of Budget & National Planning. (2017). *Economic Recovery & Growth Plan 2017-2020* (Nigeria, Ministry of Budget & National Planning). Abuja.
- Njite, D., Njoroge, J., Parsa, H., Parsa, R., & van der Rest, J. (2015). Consumer patronage and willingness-to-pay at different levels of restaurant attributes: A study from Kenya. *Research in Hospitality Management*, 5(2), 171-180.

- Nwachukwu, C. V. & Onuoha, C. (2022). Entrepreneurial Orientation and Corporate Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Lagos State, Nigeria. *International Academy Journal of Management Annals*, 6(2), 73-83
- Nyakweba, N., Wesonga, J. N., & Bosire, B. E. (2015). An analysis of factors influencing consumer patronage of bars: A survey of bars in Kisii Town's central business district, Kenya. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*, 11, 190-202.
- Octache, I. & Mahmood, R. (2015). Entrepreneurial orientation and performance of Nigerian banks. *Management Science*, 20(5), 670-651.
- Oghenevwegba, E. & Iwegbue, C. N. (2022). Impact of Entrepreneurial Orientation in the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Accounting, Finance & Management Research*, 6(10), 1-12
- Ologbenla, P. (2022). Entrepreneurial orientation and performance control attributes among SMEs in Osun State Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Studies and Social Science Research*, 4(4), 85-95
- Olowofeso, E. & Ale, O. A. (2019). Entrepreneurial Orientation and Performance of Hospitality Industry in Akure, Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 11(2), 58-65 DOI: 10.7176/EJBM
- Omhonria, D., & Needorn, R. S. (2022). Production improvement function and organizational performance of manufacturing firms in Rivers State. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 8(1), 13-29.
- Omisakin, O. M., Nakhid, T., Littrell, R., & Verbitsky, J. (2016). Entrepreneurial orientation among migrants and small and medium enterprises. *Journal of Business Administration Research*, 5(1), 7
- Patel, P. (2018). Leveraging entrepreneurial orientation to enhance SME export performance. *An Office of Advocacy Working Paper*. No.337, 1-32.
- Pfeffer, J., & Salancik, G. (1978). The external control of organizations: A resource dependence perspective. New York: Harper & Row.
- Putninš, T. J., & Sauka, A. (2020). Why Does Entrepreneurial Orientation Affect Company Performance? *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*, 14, 711–35
- Rather, R. A., Tehseen, S., Itoo, M. H. & Hussain. S. (2019). Customer Brand Identification, Affective Commitment, Customer Satisfaction, and Brand Trust as Antecedents of Customer Behavioral Intention of Loyalty: An Empirical Study in the Hospitality Sector. 196-217. 10.1080/21639159.2019.1577694.
- Rauch, A., Wiklund, J., Lumpkin, G. T. & Frese, M., (2009). Entrepreneurial Orientation and Business Performance: An Assessment of Past Research and Suggestions for the Future. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 33(3), 761-787.
- Rezaei, J., & Ortt, R. (2018). Entrepreneurial orientation and firm performance: the mediating role of functional performances. *Management Research Review*, 41(7), 878-900.
- Rochdi, D., Khatijah, O., & Muhammad, A. S. A. H. (2017). Mediating role of the innovation effectiveness on the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and the SMEs

- performance in Algeria. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 15. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17512/pjms.2017.15.1.18>
- Schumpeter, J. A. (1942). *Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy*, London: Routledge.
- Schumpeter, J. A. (2004). *The theory of economic development*. An inquiry into profits, capital, credit, interest, and the business cycle, Transaction Publishers, New Brunswick.
- Sebora, T. C. & Theerapatvong, T. (2010) Corporate entrepreneurship: a test of external and internal influences on managers' idea generation, risk taking, and pro-activeness. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 5(1), 1-20
- Shahzad, F., Lu, J., & Fareed, Z. (2019). Does firm life cycle impact corporate risk taking and performance? *Journal of Multinational Financial Management*,
- Shane, S., Kolvereid, L., & Westhead, P. (1991). An exploratory examination of the reasons leading to new firm formation across country and gender. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 6(6), 431–446. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0883-9026\(91\)90029-D](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0883-9026(91)90029-D)
- Short, J. C., Zachary, M. A., & Ketchen Jr, D. J. (2018). Entrepreneurial orientation rhetoric and franchise system size: The moderating role of military veteran recruitment. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, 10, e00097.
- Simonin, B.L., 1997. The importance of collaborative know-how: An empirical test of the learning organization. *Academy of management Journal*, 40(5),1150- 1174.
- Sorama, K. & Joensuu-Salo, S. (2023). Entrepreneurial Orientation, Firm Growth and Performance in SMEs: Testing the Scale of EO in SME Context. *Entrepreneurship Research Journal*, 13(3), 601–629
- Surroca, J., Tribó, J. A., & Waddock, S. (2010). Corporate responsibility and financial performance: The role of intangible resources. *Strategic management journal*, 31(5), 463-490.
- Uchegbulam, P., Akinyele, S. T., & Ibidunni, A. S. (2015). Competitive strategy and performance of selected SMEs in Nigeria. *International Conference on African development issues (CIJ-ICA DI)*, 326-333.
- Wales, W. J., Covin, J. G. & Monsen, E. (2020). Entrepreneurial Orientation: The necessity of a multi-level conceptualization. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*, 14, 639-660
- Wales, W. J., Sascha, K., Matthias, F., Christoph, S., & Jeffrey, G. C. (2021). The Status Quo of Research on Entrepreneurial Orientation: Conversational Landmarks and Theoretical Scaffolding. *Journal of Business Research*, 128, 564–577
- Wiklund, J., & Shepherd, D. (2005). Entrepreneurial orientation and small business performance: a configurational approach. *Journal of Business Venturing*. 20(1), 71-89.